

A Study on Problems of Small Scale Industry with Special Reference towards Dharmapuri (Dt)

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Abstract

The government is making all efforts to provide on atmosphere, level playing ground and policy support to enable the SSI sector to achieve higher levels of production, exports employment. The small-scale industry evokes different meanings for different agencies and the financial institutions. However, the definition of small industry is an important aspect of government policy as it identifies the target groups. The Micro, Small and Medium level of company Developmental act for 2006. The Act has empowered the government to establish a National Board for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise. The small-scale sector has been assigned an important role in the industrial economy of the country on account of some of its inherent advantages like low capital intensity, high employment generation capacity, regionally balanced development and even distribution of wealth and income. There are two types of simple level of the company for which registration certificates are issued by the Department of Industries and Commerce as per the guidelines issued by the Development Commissioner, Government of India, and New Delhi. The Industrial Policy Resolution, Five Year Plans and recommendation of different committees on SSIs focus on the need for adequate and timely delivery of credit to the SSIs sector by commercial banks. The increase in the working capital limits, as suggested by different committees on the financing of SSI units, would ease the flow of bank credit to the small-scale industry.

Keywords: Small scale industry: Developmental plan: Employees relationship: Problems of that particular industry.

Introduction

The small-scale industry is to play in a vital role in the development of the industry of our nation. This type of industry is to provide on various level of opportunity in our society like on various people are to getting on emplacement chance that way to developing on people standard living level and that improve on the economic level of the people. The government also provide various level of help to the development of an in that small scale industry like that help are in finance level, marketing facility, export level of the facility, production facility, raw material buying facility etc..

Problems Faced By Small Scale Industries

Some of the major Problem faced for on small-scale industry are

1. Production Problems,
2. Technological Problems,
3. Infrastructural Problems,
4. Survival Problems,
5. Managerial Problems,
6. Marketing Problems,
7. Financial Problems,
8. Labor Problems.
9. Project planning
10. Idle capacity
11. Political problem
12. Government problem
13. Inadequate finance
14. Export of production problem
15. Poor industrial relationship
16. Environmental problem

Production Problem

The raw material required by the small-scale industries may not be available in nearby places or may not be available in abundance.

SSI may not have adequate storing capacity. Hence, goods cannot be purchased in bulk and stored in large quantity. An inadequate infrastructural facility creates the problem of acute shortage of basic raw materials if it has to be imported from distant places.

Small-scale enterprises are unable to make full utilization of plant capacity as they face the shortage of power supply. This affects their manufacturing progress. They could not afford to install their power plant due to the shortage of capital.

Technology Problem

Small-scale industries do not have adequate funds to spend on the latest technologies or sophisticated technologies. Hence, they face technological problems due to the traditional technology adopted by them. Due to old technology either production process may be slow or there may not be demand for the products produced by SSI.

Infrastructure Facility

Small-scale industries are set up in rural and backward areas as incentives are given by the government for setting up of industries in these areas; These areas may not have good roads, goods warehouses, proper transportation, proper established channels of telecommunication and adequate supply of power. Lack of any of this facility can cause potential damage to the firm's value chain process.

Survival Problem

Inadequate marketing facilities, lack of funds, etc., affect the long run profit earning capacity of SSI. SSI generates less return on investment and affects the chances of survival of enterprises run by small-scale entrepreneurs.

Many Problem Faced by on Management

The entrepreneur has to perform various managerial functions without having any exposure to professional education or formal training. SSI cannot recruit various people for carrying out managerial functions like large-scale industries.

Marketing Problem

Large-scale industries can spend a lot of money on marketing. Whereas the small-scale industries may lack it. Hence, they cannot establish their name on small-scale industry

Under Utilization of Capacity

In that rural area should have that no adequate facility for that fully utilization of an all that capacity in that company management like,

- Raw material problems
- Finance problem
- Inadequate knowledge employees

Project Planning

The inadequate level of on project planning facility in that rural area it's not for on developmental area that way for not to getting on infrastructure project planning and also in production facility planning facility project.

Idle Capacity

The rural area also to giving that various level of capacity on here but it that environment are not to help to expose that is capacity. So that various capacity is not to use in that place. This is capacity is idle of in Small-scale industry area.

Political Problem

In that rural place, small-scale industry is facing that various level of on political problem because of this is on a rural place so, the political problem enter in our industry. So, when that small-scale industry is facing that problem is on majorly in that rural place.

Government Problem

The government provides that various level of new procedure are to implemental in at various time that rules and regulation are to provide in on a sick level of that company like
Money devalue
GST problem etc..

Inadequate Finance

Finance is on a major problem are developing on our small-scale industry, because in that rural area are not to getting on immediately finance help to that industry purpose. So the small-scale industry is facing that this problem is on majorly.

Export of Production Problem

Another major problem to be faced in on small-scale industry is in transportation In that transportation are helps to provide on the export of on production of material or product in that industry. But the rural area small-scale industry is not to get on the efficient level of the transportation facility. So the scale industry faced on exportation problems.

Poor Industrial Relationship

The industrial relationship is on at most important in on industrial developmental purpose, but here on rural area's are located in the minimum level of industry, So, the rural area small-scale industry in on creating on the lower level of ion industrial relationship.

Environmental Problem

In rural area environment are faced in on many problems. The rural area is located in a maximum level of agricultural land and river here, in industrial area's wastages are collared in that land and water so, to faced in this type of problem in our small-scale industry.

Table 1 Level of growth in last five year in Dharmapuri area's SSIs sectors

S.No	Year	Industry Type	Developing Level
1.	2014	Manufacturing in SSI	3.6
2.	2015	Manufacturing in SSI	4.7
3.	2016	Manufacturing in SSI	5.3
4.	2017	Manufacturing in SSI	5.8
5.	2018	Manufacturing in SSI	7.6

Source: SSI Developmental Sector Tamilnadu

Table

S.No	Type of Problems Faced by on SSI	%
1.	Finance problem	40%
2.	Infrastructure	10
3.	Marketing	10
4.	Export facility	5%
5.	Transport facility	5%
6.	Technology Level	10%
7.	Employees Knowledge	20%

Source: SSI Developmental Sector

Conclusion

The small-scale industry is mostly to faced in on marketing problems and then finance and also labor knowledge of the particular industry. When that government is to reduce on finance problem and then to arrange on marketing facility in small-scale industry. The Tamilnadu state government are allocating on 2.5 core in developing on small-scale industry around on Tamilnadu state. So, The government is provide on this facility for developing on SSI sector.

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